

ASAP CRN Cloud Release - v4.1.1

DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.20185963](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20185963)

Overview

This **v4.1.1** Data Release for the CRN Cloud completes the release of additional un-curated PMDBS data, including long-read whole genome sequencing and midbrain hybrid selection sequencing from Team Scherzer, and sample-multiplexed multimodal, RNAseq, and ATACseq Datasets from a variety of assays from Team Voet.

New Datasets

- scherzer-pmdbs-lr-wgs, DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.19124632](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19124632)
- scherzer-pmdbs-sn-rnaseq-midbrain-hybsel, DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.19124469](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19124469)
- voet-pmdbs-sn-multimodal, DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.18988753](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18988753)
- voet-pmdbs-sn-atacseq-scalebio-hydrop, DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.18988743](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18988743)
- voet-pmdbs-sn-atacseq-scalebio-10x, DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.18988717](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18988717)
- voet-pmdbs-sn-atacseq-hydrop, DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.18988735](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18988735)
- voet-pmdbs-sn-atacseq-10x, DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.18988729](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18988729)
- voet-pmdbs-sn-rnaseq-parsebio, DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.18988761](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18988761)
- voet-pmdbs-sn-rnaseq, DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.18988768](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18988768)

Data Release Date: 2026-05-30

ASAP Teams: Team Scherzer & Team Voet. See [CRN Cloud Authorship List](#) for the full list of contributing investigators/researchers by dataset.

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